

AGRICULTURE AND ITS EFFECTS ON RURAL ECONOMICAL DEVELOPMENT OF KUSAVLI VILLAGE, IN MAWAL TAHSIL IN PUNE DISTRICT (MAHARASHTRA)

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Abstract:

Agriculture is most roles for rural economical development. This paper represents agriculture with help of land holding capacity land use pattern, farmers, agriculture labors, Marginal Workers how effects on rural economical development.

The study was carrying out on the basis of primary data including the field survey with help of questioners and also collect the secondary data from grampanchayat of kusavali village. This paper represent the Agriculture and its effects on Kusavali village with help of following parameters like Agricultural Labor, Live Stock, Farmers in study area., Marginal Workers in study area, Total Man Power, General land use of Kusavali, and Land holding capacity.

Key Words:- *Field Survey, Spatial Analysis, Maps, graphs and Tables.*

1. Introduction:

Agriculture is important and largest sector of Indian economy. Near about 65% population in India is engaged in agriculture activities. So agriculture is the primary activity. due to more than population involve In primary activity. Agriculture is helpfully on rural economical development. Because agriculture related occupation like transportation, animal rearing and increasing job like agriculture labors, open seeds stores and others. Shrouding the rural area in developed agro base Industries like rice mill, cotton mill, dairy frames and other.

Due to agriculture is most effective on rural economical development.

2. Objectives of study area.

- To find out the agriculture effects on rural economi in study area.

3. Methodology:

The primary data and secondary data have been used for the research paper. The questionnaire has been prepared to collect the data. The statistical method has been used for data calculation.

3.1. Data collection and management:

Data collection has done with the help of the observation, interviews, photos, Google images and field survey. Questionnaires have prepared for obtaining information of solid waste& tin-bin system. However spatial analysis of study area has been done on Google image using Arc GIS in to calculate area and related features.

4. Study of agriculture effect on kusavli village

4. 1. Family wise Land holding capacity in study area :

Easy and suitable practice requires the optimum holding which can be managed by the working family members well as the supporting live stock and the machinery.

Here in the village of Kusavali 72 families are residing. The land holding capacity of 24 families is between 2 acres to 4 acres. The land holding capacity of 9 families is between 5 acres to 10 acres, and 2 families having above 10 acres land holding capacity.

Table No:1 Agriculture

Area Of Land (Acres)	Number Of Land Holder	Percentage
0-1	37	51.37%
2-4	24	33.33
5-10	9	12.50
Above 10	2	2.77
TOTAL	72	100.00

4.2. General land use of Kusavali Village

The agriculture activity in the Kusavali is totally on monsoon dependent. Irrigation facility is not available in the village due to poverty of families. The total geographical area of village is 82 acre. This area has been utilized by following ways.

In the study area total land acre 82 acre. Divided many land use types. Agriculture land use 51.22% as well as under the forest is 24.39% therefore more than largest area covered by agriculture land use and minimum area covered by non agricultural land and is 10.98%

Table no.2: Agriculture and land use

Use of Land	Area In Acres	% Area
Agriculture	42	51.22
Fallow Land	11	12.5
Not for Agriculture	09	10.98
Forest	20	24.39
Total Land in acres	82	100

4.3. Gender wise Man Power of kusavli village:

The above table shows the distribution of main workers during the year 2015. We can conclude from the studied data that in the year 2015 the percentage of male workforce 54.37% and female workforce is 45.63 % in that case we see that female workforce is less and male workforce is more.

Table No.3: Gender wise Man Power

Gender	Population	Percentage (360)
Male	137	195.71
Female	115	164.29
Total	252	360

4.4. Marginal Workers in study area.

We find in village Kusavali most of the people do not have enough land which they can still on their own to earn and living so they are mostly dependent on the other works that available to them. According to survey there are 36 (83.72%) Male and 7 (16.28%) female are found as a marginal workers.

Table No. 4: Marginal Workers

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	36	83.72%
Female	7	16.28%
Total	43	100

4.5. Gender wise Farmers:

In rural main occupation of people is farming. They either work in their own land or for somebody else. There are 177 farmers in 2015 out of which 88(49.72. %) are male & 89 (50.28%) are female farmers.

Table No.5: Gender wise Farmers:

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	88	49.72
Female	89	50.28
Total	177	100

4.6. Gender wise Agricultural Labor in study area

From the above table it can be shown that in Agricultural Labour males are more which contribute 58.62% than females which contribute 41.38%.

Table No.6: Gender wise Agriculture Labour

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	34	58.62
Female	24	41.38
Total	58	100

4.7. Live Stock in study area.

It is observed that most of the villages have at list one domestic animal in their houses. Bullocks are used plunging and for Bullocks carts. The cow and buffalo are kept for milk and cow dung. Those we observed that most of the primarily need are meet by this domestic animals.

The study area total 194 animals (live stock) are higher quantity is 40.21% of Goat and Sheep and lowest quantity 4.64% is of Buffalos

Table no. 7: Live Stock

Animal	No. of Animal	Percentage (%)
Cow	25	12.89
Buffalo	9	4.64
Goat & Sheep	78	40.21
Ox	47	24.23
Hen	35	18.04
Total	194	100

5. Conclusion:

The aims & objectives stated for this study which has be supportively elaborated and interpreted by the many finding and conclusion driven the various ways of this study. The conclusions were elaborated in the following ways.

In Kusavali 85% people depend upon agriculture. In the process of general economic development, agriculture contributes 90%. It is therefore necessary and useful to acquaint it plays in the economic development. This will provide us a frame to discuss the present position for the development and progress. Rice is a major crop in the study area as well as wheat, maize, oil seeds, cereals is crop pattern of the study area. And there developed animal rearing in like cow, buffalo, ox and other.

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